

DESIGN OF MULTI BAND MIMO ANTENNA FOR VARIOUS INDOOR APPLICATIONS

R. VASIM AKRAM, C. MURALI MOHAN, P. RADHA

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR^{1,2,3}

vasim487@gmail.com, cmmgtl68@gmail.com, radhasvec@gmail.com

Department of ECE, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

ABSTRACT: A new planar multiband multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) antenna is introduced, which is both innovative and very compact. Two symmetrical radiating components, linked by a neutralising line to eliminate reactive coupling, make up the suggested antenna. The radiating element, which consists of a folded monopole and a bevelled rectangular metal patch, is intended to operate at several frequencies, including GSM 900 MHz, DCS 1800 MHz, LTE-E 2300 MHz, and LTE-D 2600 MHz. A set of 50 coplanar waveguide (CPW) transmission wires feed the antenna that is being given. The mutual coupling is reduced by engraving four apertures onto the ground plane. All of the observed parameters—impedance matching, isolation, peak gain, and radiation patterns—are satisfactory for the suggested antenna. The diversity gain (DG) and radiation efficiency (RE) at the service frequencies are satisfactory. Three different antenna feed systems are covered in the Ericsson indoor experiment. The suggested antenna performs well in terms of download and upload speeds, as well as Long Term Evolution (LTE) reference signal receiving power (RSRP).

Keywords: Multiband, multiple-input–multiple-output (MIMO) antenna, Long Term Evolution (LTE), indoor, antenna feed system

Introduction:

When looking to expand the capacity of a system, one option is to implement MIMO (Multiple Input and Multiple Output) antenna systems. These systems

offer high bandwidth, reduce fading caused by multipath effects, and improve spectral efficiency and reliability. Thanks to the addition of a number of antennas to the transceiver, which transmits and receives power via multiple antennas, exceptionally high data rates are obtained in MIMO antenna systems. Various MIMO antenna configurations have been covered in the literature [1–5]. The multi-input and multi-output antenna design is very critical for portable devices.

tiny and will have little signal connection with one another. Coupling effects provide the greatest challenge to MIMO antenna designers. To fit in a small system, the radiating elements of a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) antenna must be near to each other; as a result, the energy emitted from each element will interfere with each other, leading to far field coupling [6-8]. Especially in bands like lower wide bands, this impact will significantly degrade system performance. Improving the inter-radiating element distance is an effective strategy for dampening coupling effects[9, 10]. To reduce the inner gap between the radiating components while maintaining optimum performance, decoupling structures may be employed between the radiators. There are a number of methods that have been suggested by antenna engineers to increase the separation of antenna components using EBS and DGS structures [11, 12]. There are two subtypes of decoupling techniques based on operating principles. One kind uses metamaterials[13–14] and structures with a defective ground to reduce currents among radiating components. By efficiently dampening surface waves, metamaterials increase isolation between antennas; structures with defective ground may achieve a high degree of isolation; and metamaterials with single or multiple[15–16] opening slots can function as band stop filters. A second approach to achieve isolation is to introduce a second coupling channel that mimics the first one[17–20].

Inserting components like parasitic elements, decoupling networks, and neutralisation lines between the radiating elements can also improve isolation [21–24]. In the case of two closely placed antennas, a bandwidth that is off by less than 5%, and an isolation of 20 dB. As an efficient means of achieving high isolation, decoupling networks make use of suspended lines and lumped elements as their active components. Using second-order coupling resonators is another approach to achieve isolation for 20 dB and 10% bandwidth. Several works of literature with three linear neutralisation actualized with dual radiating elements [26–28] and the usage of only lines to reduce mutual coupling by 20 dB and bandwidth by 10% are examples of alternatives to networks for decoupling and neutralisation, respectively, [25]. However, techniques like decoupling structures are still challenging, and isolation levels are poor—not even close to -15 dB. A folded neutralisation approach may be used in antennas with a separation of $0.3 \lambda_0$ to

enhance the isolation bandwidth. Nevertheless, it is not feasible to build it for use with two or more closely placed antennas that are less than $0.1\lambda_0$ apart.

At 30 dB, the levels of isolation are not achievable. Although the neutralisation lines and decoupling networks may reach a small size, none of the aforementioned technologies are flexible enough to meet the needs of all possible applications [29–34]. The following are some of the ways in which this work contributes:

- The Multi-band MIMO antenna described in this article has a neutralisation link and slits that connect two antennas that share a coplanar waveguide feed.
- Several indoor applications, including as LTE, W-LAN, and WiMax, have shown acceptable total active reflection coefficient and envelope correlation coefficient values, as well as satisfactory impedance matching and diversity gain.

1. Antenna Geometry:

The Fig.1 represents the geometrical structure of CPW layered MIMO antenna iterations 1 and 2 which has radiating elements in square shape. The antenna is fabricated on FR4 substrate with 4.4 dielectric values and 0.02 loss tangent with dimensions of $L \times W \times h$. The patch on the substrate is intended by square with split ring resonator and CPW loaded at the ground with a sharp pencil like shape feed line with 50 Ohm impedance is incorporated. Fig. 1(a) shows the geometry and configuration of the proposed antenna. It was fabricated on a $60 \times 80 \times 0.8$ mm FR4 epoxy substrate with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 4.4$ and loss tangent $\tan \delta = 0.02$. The antenna consists of two symmetrical radiating elements. The coplanar waveguide (CPW) transmission lines of 50 Ω feed the radiating

elements connected by a 1 mm wide shorting line. The shorting line takes the role of neutralizing the currents from two elements to increase their isolation. As shown in Fig. 1(b), four 30 mm long slits and two 2×12 mm² rectangles are cut from the backside of the ground plane for reducing the mutual coupling and slightly improving the impedance matching. In Fig. 1(c), the left folded monopole of the radiating element provides the 900 MHz, 1800 MHz and 2300 MHz resonant path, while the right beveled rectangular metal patch is the 2600 MHz resonant path. Hence, the overall operating frequency bands of each radiating element are achieved as GSM 900 MHz, DCS 1800 MHz, LTE-E 2300 MHz and LTE-D 2600 MHz.

From the equation 1 the resonant frequency is calculated.

$$f_r = \frac{144}{Lg + Pl + Pg + \frac{A_1}{2\pi Lg\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} + \frac{A_2}{2\pi Pl\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}}} \quad (1)$$

Fig.1: Geometries of the proposed multi band MIMO antenna.(a) Front view.(b) Rearview.
(c)Detailed view (d)&(e) isometric view design

Where L_g represents the ground plane length, PL is the patch length, P_g is the gap among the ground and patch, A_1 denotes the area of the ground plane, A_2 denotes patch area, ϵ_{eff} denotes the dielectric value effective where is $\epsilon_{\text{eff}} = (\epsilon_r + 1)/2$. To recover the isolation among the 2 ports the L-shaped long slots are designed in the structure. In the ground plane two slots which acts as $\lambda/4$ resonators are included to achieve band at WLAN frequency. The

Fig. 1 shows the dimensions and structure of the designed antenna which its parameters. The length and width of the proposed antenna is $60 \times 80 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$ with the thickness of 0.8 mm^3 . Addition of neutralising link, this links the two radiating elements and cancel the mutual coupling between elements and

Etching four slits and two small rectangles into the ground plane which yields good isolation in all the serving frequencies

2. Analysis and Results:

The projected CPW

layered MIMO antenna iterations 1 and 2 exhibit two operational frequency bands conferred, and two operational frequencies was designed, and simulated results are taken by using the HFSS software. The resonant frequencies area with return loss less than -10dB with the 2.1GHz to 5 GHz and 6GHz to 12 GHz bands shown in the Fig. 4 and 5. The fabricated antenna results are measured by using network vector

analyzer with anechoic chamber. The designed antennas performance with simulated and measured results gives good performance when both are compared. The Fig.4 shows the simulated and measured results of the designed antenna iteration 1 with the reflection coefficient plotted in it. The Fig.5 shows the simulated and measured results of the designed antenna iteration 2 with the reflection coefficient plotted in it. The measured reflection coefficient operates at certain frequencies are 2.1GHz to 5 GHz. The mutual coupling at the resonant frequencies 2GHz to 5 GHz is 5dB and -20dB.

Figure 2: Results of return loss plot

In figure 2, the return loss characteristics of proposed multi band MIMO antenna with various substrate materials is depicted. The substrate material chosen for the analysis are arlon, FR4 and RTduroid 5880. From the figure it is clearly observed that the proposed structure is having very good

impedance matching when FR4 is used as substrate when compared with arlon and RTduroid. In figure 2, the return loss characteristics of the proposed multi band MIMO antenna is depicted from that it is clearly seen that proposed antenna without the complementary split

ring resonator can operate in the same multiple bands with some decent impedance matching, when the Complementary rings are etched the impedance matching at the higher band is

reduced and when the complementary ring is converted in to complementary split ring resonator the proposed multi band MIMO antenna can able to achieve very good impedance matching at the higher bands.

Figure3: Results of isolation plot

In figure 3, the isolation performance of the proposed multiband MIMO antenna is depicted. From the figure it is observed that the isolation level is maintained at the lower band and at the higher band the isolation is greater than 20 dB. In the higher bands after the inclusion of the CSRR at the radiating element. To analyze the working mechanism of the neutralizing line and four slits, Fig. 3 shows the simulated $|S_{21}|$ of MIMO antennas with different decoupling configurations. It can be observed that the isolation is deteriorated seriously in the operating bands, when MIMO antenna without neutralizing line and four slits. The isolation is greatly improved in the DCS 1800 MHz and LTE-E 2300 MHz bands when MIMO antenna with neutralizing line. Moreover, the coupling can be further decreased in the GSM 900 MHz and LTE-D

2600 MHz bands when MIMO antenna with four slits etched into the back ground plane. In figure 4, the 3D radiation pattern is presented; it is observed that the maximum radiation intensity is perpendicular to the antenna axis. From the figure it is observed that most of the surface current is altered because of the inclusion of complementary split ring resonator. It is noted that most of the surface current is accumulated near the three complementary split ring resonators. As observed, the radiation efficiencies are 85% to 95% high in the operating frequency bands. When one port is excited and the other port is terminated by a 50Ω load, the

measured radiation patterns of the antenna on y-z plane and x-y plane for four different frequencies

900, 1800, 2300 and 2600 MHz.

Figure4: Results of gain plot (3D)

Figure5: results of TARC plot

By energizing two indistinguishable antennas with by placing front to front position of in the fields as far, the interruption was taken down and displayed of proposed model antenna in Fig5. Right now, port1 was energized then port2 was ended with 50Ω impedance and when port2 was energized then port1 was

ended with 50Ω impedance. Group delay is flat in the measured operating bands. Sharp edges are observed at the bands in the TARC graph.

Figure6: RESULTS OF VSWR PLOT

In figure 6, the simulated VSWR plot is depicted from which it is observed that the value of VSWR is less than 2 in the operating ranges 2.01 GHz to 2.69 GHz

GHz to 4.26 GHz which is used for WiMAX and UAV application and GSM 900 MHz, DCS 1800 MHz, LTE-E 2300 MHz and LTE-D 2600 MHz applications

which is used for ISM application, 3.54 respectively.

Figure7:RESULTSOFECCPLOT

$$Ecc = \frac{|S_{11}S_{12} + S_{21}S_{22}|}{(1 - (|S_{11}|^2 + |S_{21}|^2))(1 - (|S_{22}|^2 + |S_{12}|^2))} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Diversity Gain} = 10 \log(1 - ECC^2) \quad (3)$$

To assess the performance in diversity Envelope relationship coefficient (ECC) parameter is used. The below equations 2 and 3 are the ECC and diversity gain values obtained from the reflection coefficients of the designed iterations of the antenna. By minimizing the standards of ECC, the

radiation pattern overlapping can be decreased. The proposed MIMO antenna iteration 1 and 2 ECC graph is shown in Fig. 7. The acceptable value of the ECC is 0.5 and the ECC at the operating band is obtained about 0.02 at the average when there is notch in the bands.

Figure 8: RESULTS OF DG PLOT

The Fig. 8 shows the diversity gain of the designed antenna. The gain vs frequency graph is presented which clearly shows the proposed tri band MIMO antenna is having a reasonable gain in all the operating bands 2.01 GHz to 2.69 GHz which is

used for ISM application, 3.54 GHz to 4.26 GHz which is used for WiMAX and UAV application. The maximum gain of the proposed tri band MIMO antenna is 6 dBi.

Table 1: Results analysis of different methods

Name	TARC	Diversity Gain	ECC
MIMO ANTENNA WITHOUT NEUTRALISATION LINK AND SLITS	-2.4dB	8.35dB	0.81
MIMO ANTENNA WITH NEUTRALISATION LINK AND SLITS	-7.4dB	9.75dB	0.24

Conclusion: An enhanced multi-band MIMO antenna with slits and a neutralisation connection is shown in this study. The antenna's characteristics include Total Active Reflectivity Coefficient (TARC), Envelope Correlation, and others.

High Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS) software is used to model ECC and DG. To lessen the coupling mutual impact between the radiating components, we provide a meta-material based two-multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) antenna with CPW loading and FSS for gain improvement. This study proposes a new small MIMO antenna for indoor multiband applications. A multi-band antenna

element is achieved by folding a monopole and using a bevelled rectangular metal pattern. By using a neutralising line and cutting four slits in the back ground plane, a high isolation of $|S_{21}|$ -30 dB in the working bands is accomplished. Presented below are the findings on s-parameters, peak gains, and radiation patterns. Research has been focused on the diversity performance metrics of radiation efficiency and diversity gain. In addition, LTE base stations with three different antenna feed methods are built to assess the performance of the proposed MIMO antenna in a real-life LTE indoor application. Indoor GSM, DCS, and LTE use cases might benefit from the suggested antenna.

References:

- [1]. 1. Naga Vaishnavi, D., Radhakrishna, P., Bharath, N., Madhuri, K., Bhavani Prasad, K. & Harish, K. 2015, "Flared V-shape slotted monopole multiband antenna with metamaterial loading", International Journal on Communications Antenna and Propagation, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 93-97.
- [2]. Bhavani, K.V.L., Khan, H. 2015, "Multiband slotted aperture antenna with defected ground structure for C and X-band communication applications", Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 454-461.
- [3]. Lakshmi, M.L.S.N.S., Khan, H. 2015, "Novel sequential rotated 2×2 array notched circular patch antenna", Journal of Engineering Science and Technology Review, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 73-77.
- [4]. Lakshmikanth, P., Takeshore, K. 2015, "Printed log-periodic dipole antenna with notched filter at 2.45 GHz frequency for wireless communication applications", Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 40-44.
- [5]. A., Bhargav, Y., Dinesh Naga Venkata Sai, U. & Feeraz, S. 2014, "Measurement of dimensional characteristics of microstrip antenna based on mathematical formulation", International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 1063-1074.
- [6]. Kartheek, T., Kaza, V.L., Prasanth, S., Chandra Sikakollu, K.S.S., Thammishetti, M., Srinivas, A. & Bhavani, K.V.L. 2015, "Novel printed monopole trapezoidal notch

- antenna with S-band rejection", Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, vol. 76, no. 1, pp. 42-49.
- [7]. K., Sriharsha, N., Jaswanth Kumar, J., Siddharth, D.S. & Sai Teja Reddy, D. 2015, "Design and analysis of compact coplanar wave guide fed asymmetric monopole antennas", Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 247-252.
- [8]. Khan, H. & Kotamraju, S.K. 2016, "Circularly polarized slotted aperture antenna with coplanar waveguide fed for broadband applications", Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 267-277.
- [9]. Ujwala, D., Bhavani Sankar, Y., Kandepi, M., Nagendra Reddy, A.S. & Nagajyothi, D. 2013, "CPW fed serrated antenna performance based on substrate permittivity", International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1349-1354.
- [10]. Manikanta, P., Narendra, K., Kishore, M.R. & Kiran, G. 2014, "Tapered step CPW-fed antenna for wideband applications", ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 9, no. 10, pp. 1967-1973.
- [11]. G.S., Kumar, K.V.V., Rahul, R. & Srikanth, V. 2014, "Fractal aperture
- EBG ground structured dual band planar slot antenna", International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 515-524.
- [12]. Kumar, K.V.V. & Manjusha, A.V. 2014, "Analysis of CPW fed step serrated ultra wide band antenna on Rogers RT/duroid substrates", International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 53-58.
- [13]. A., Prasanth, S., Krishna, B.M.S., Manikantha, D. & Naga Sai, U.S. 2015, "Analysis of defected ground structure notched monopole antenna", ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 747-752.
- [14]. Mohan Reddy, S.S., Sanjay, B. & Ujwala, D. 2013, "Trident shaped ultra wideband antenna analysis based on substrate permittivity", International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1355-1361.
- [15]. S.S., Sharma, N., Ravindranath Chowdary, J., Pavithra, B.R., Kishore, K.N.V.S., Sriram, G. & Sachin Kumar, B. 2013, "Performance characterization of radial stub microstrip bow-tie antenna", International Journal of Engineering and Technology, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 760-764.

- [16].Khan, H. &Ujwala, D. 2014, "Fractal shaped Sierpinski on EBG structured ground plane", Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies, vol. 13, no. 25, pp. 26-35.
- [17]. Pranoop, M.S., Bose, K.S.N.M.C. & Kumar, B.S. 2015, "Cpw fed antenna for wideband applications based on tapered step ground and ebgstructure", Indian Journal of Science and Technology, vol. 8, pp. 119-127.
- [18]. Mohan Reddy, S.S., Mallikarjuna Rao, P. 2015, "Asymmetric defected ground structured monopole antenna for wideband communication systems", International Journal on Communications Antenna and Propagation, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 256-262.
- [19]. Murthy, K., Umakantham, K., Murthy, K.S. 2017, "Reconfigurable notch band monopole slot antenna for WLAN/IEEE-802.11n applications", International Journal of Intelligent Engineering and Systems, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 166-173.
- [20]. Raman, Y.S.V., Mounika, G., Sai Teja, K., Sai Kumar, S.B.V.N. & Sri Harsha, K.2016, "Analysis of circularly polarized notch band antenna with DGS", ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 11, no. 17, pp. 10140-10150.
- [21].Ramkiran,D.S.,Harsha,N.S.,Vardhan,V.,Avinash,K.,Chaitanya,M.N.&Nagasai, U.S.2015,"Novelcompactasymmetric alfractal apertureNotchbandantenna",Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies, vol. 14, no. 27, pp. 1-12.
- [22].Sadasivarao, B. & Madhav, B.T.P. 2014, "Analysis of hybrid slot antenna based on substratepermittivity",ARPNJournal ofEngineeringandAppliedSciences,vol. 9,no.6, pp.885-890.
- [23]. Sreenivasa Rao, D., Lakshmi Narayana, J., K., Anil Kumar, B. & Karthik, G. 2016, "Microstrip parasitic strip loaded reconfigurable monopole antenna", ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 11, no. 19, pp. 11589-11594.
- [24]. D., Haritha, N., Ramya, R.S., Vindhya, K.M. & Abhishek, S.P. 2014, "Design and analysis of microstrip slot array antenna configuration for bandwidth enhancement", Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies, vol. 13, no. 25, pp. 72-83.
- [25]. Srinivas, M.S.S.S., Ramakrishna, T.V., Bhagyalakshmi, N., Madhavi, S. &Venkateswarulu, K. 2015, "A novel compact CPW fed slot antenna with EBG structure", ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 835- 841.

- [26]. Sunder, P.S., Kotamraju, S.K., Ramakrishna, T.V., Sruthi, T.S., Vivek, P., Kumar, J.J. & Dileep, M. 2015, "Novel miniaturized wide band annular slot monopole antenna", Far East Journal of Electronics and Communications, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 149-159.
- [27]. B.T.P. Madhav, K.V. Vineetha, Meghana, D. Arun Kumar Reddy, M.C.Rao, Sudipta Das, Circular Monopole with Star Shaped Etched Antenna for PCS, UMTS and WI-FI Applications, International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, Vol. 29, No. 4s, 2020, pp. 2046-2056.
- [28]. Lakrit S, Das S, Ghosh S, B T P Madhav, Compact UWB flexible elliptical CPW-fed antenna with triple notch bands for wireless communications, International Journal of RF Microwave Computer Aided Engineering, 2020, e22201, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mmce.22201>.
- [29]. S. Lakrit, S. Das, K. Vasu Babu, An octagonal star shaped flexible UWB antenna with band-notched characteristics for WLAN applications, JINST, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/15/02/P02021>.
- [30]. T. Anilkumar, B.T.P. Madhav, M. Venkateswara Rao, B. PrudhviNadh, Bandwidth Reconfigurable Antenna on a Liquid Crystal Polymer substrate for Automotive Communication Applications, International Journal of Electronics and Communications (2020), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeue.2020.153096>.
- [31]. K V Vineetha, A Durga Sindhu, B Sruthi Anmisha, T Balaji, CPW-Fed OctagonShaped Ring Slot Monopole Antenna, International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research Volume 9, Issue 01, January 2020, pp 616-626.
- [32]. B T P Madhav, T Anilkumar, Vanga Vaishnavi, Talasila Bharath Chand, Switchable Fractal Antenna for LTE and Vehicular IoT Communication Platforms, International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research, Volume 8, Issue 11, November 2019, pp 1044-1047.
- [33]. T Anilkumar, YepuriSpoorthiHawanika, M Venkateswara Rao, B PrudhviNadh, Flexible Liquid Crystal Polymer Based Conformal Fractal Antenna for Internet of Vehicles (IoV) Applications, International Journal of Microwave and Optical Technology, Vol 14, No 6, Nov 2019, pp 423-430.
- [34]. S. Bandi, D.K. Nayak, S.S.M. Reddy, Compact flexible inkjet-printing antenna on paper and transparent PET substrate materials for vehicular instrument communication.